

INDUSTRIAL REQUIREMENT AND BUSINESS EDUCATION CURRICULUM AS CORRELATE FOR EMPLOYMENT OF BUSINESS EDUCATION GRADUATES IN NORTH-EAST, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed at investigating the correlation between industrial requirement and business education curriculum for employment of business education graduates in north-east, Nigeria. To achieve this, the study used three objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses. The population of the study 276 respondents, out of this number, 60 were business education lecturers and 216 were postgraduate students from three Federal Institution in the North-east, Nigeria. These institutions were Modibbo Adama University, Yola, University of Maiduguri and Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University respectively. The study used the entire population as sample. This is because of the relatively small numbers of respondent involve in the study. Descriptive survey was used as a designed. While Structured Questionnaire were used as an instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was structured into two sections. Section A was used to illicit information on the bio data of the responded whereas the section B was used to illicit information on the questionnaire items of the study. The instruments were validated by two experts whom were not below the rank of a senior lecturer from the Department of Vocational Education. The collected data was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used for answering the research questions, while inferential statistics of a linear regression analysis was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. All those hypotheses with a P-value of less than the Alpha value at 0.05 level of significance, were rejected. While those hypotheses with p-value above 0.05 level of significance were retained. The findings of the study revealed that industrial requirement and business education curriculum had a positive relationship with an employment opportunity of business education graduates in north-east, Nigeria. The study recommended that, University administration should emphasize more on students' skills acquisition as this was found to be a requirement for the industrial employment opportunities for business education graduates. Equipping the students with skills is tantamount to given them an industrial job.

Keywords: Industrial Requirement, Business Education Curriculum, Employment Opportunities

INTRODUCTION

In the ever-evolving landscape of education and industry, the alignment between academic curriculum and industrial requirements is crucial for producing skilled graduates capable of meeting the demands of the job market. This issue is particularly pertinent in Federal Universities in North East Nigeria, where the need to bridge the gap between what students are taught and what the industry demands is paramount for economic growth and development (Adamu, 2019). Industrial workplaces are dynamic environments that demand a specific set of skills and qualities from their workforce to ensure optimal performance, efficiency, and a positive work culture. The interplay of skills, knowledge attitude and aptitude forms the

backbone of a successful industrial workforce. Technical skills are the cornerstone of industrial work. Employees need to possess specialized knowledge and proficiency in areas such as machinery operation, technical troubleshooting, engineering, or computer programming (Smith, 2020). These skills knowledge attitude and aptitude are crucial for executing complex tasks, maintaining equipment, and ensuring the smooth operation of industrial processes.

The industrial landscape in North East Nigeria has undergone significant transformations in recent years, with emerging sectors and changing technological landscapes redefining the skills knowledge attitude and aptitude needed in the workforce (Ibrahim, 2020). Concurrently, the business education curriculum in Federal Universities has been a subject of continuous evaluation and modification to meet contemporary educational standards (Okorie, 2018). However, a comprehensive understanding of the extent to which these curriculum revisions align with the dynamic needs of the regional industries is lacking. There is a growing concern that the business education curriculum might not be adequately preparing students to meet the industrial requirements of the region, leading to challenges in employability and economic development (Yusuf, 2021). By examining the existing curriculum structures and juxtaposing them against the real-time needs of the local industries, this shed light on the discrepancies and gaps that exist. Understanding these disparities is fundamental not only for educational institutions to enhance their curriculum but also for industries to communicate their requirements effectively (Abdullahi, 2017).

The evolution of education curriculum can be traced back to ancient civilizations, where formalized systems of education began to emerge (Smith, 2005). Over centuries, curriculum development has been influenced by social, cultural, political, and economic factors, leading to diverse educational approaches and philosophies (Schubert, 2017). Education curricula consist of essential components such as learning objectives, content, instructional strategies, assessment methods, and technology integration (Marsh, 2009). These components are intricately connected, influencing one another to create a holistic and effective learning experience for students (Glatthorn, 2017). Curriculum refers to the means and materials with which students will interact for the purpose of achieving identified educational outcomes. To determine what constitutes those means and materials, educators must decide what we want the curriculum to yield. We must also ask what will constitute the “educated” individual in our society. The body of a curriculum is principally meant to enable students to meet the needs of the society and encourage positive change and growth. As Ethis and Clement (2016) observed, the curriculum categories employed by most educational institutions include: explicit, implicit, null, and extra/co-curricular. Business education aptly employs the explicit curriculums because its subjects promote the skills and knowledge that student are expected to acquire. Because this is the core purpose of running the programme, it is expected that sufficient attention and resources will be devoted to the programme (Ehis & Clement 2016).

Business education plays a pivotal role in shaping the skills, knowledge, attitudes and aptitude of future professionals, entrepreneurs, and leaders in the corporate world. The business education curriculum is designed to provide students with a holistic understanding of various aspects of business, including management, finance, marketing, entrepreneurship, and ethics. Business education curricula typically include core subjects such as accounting, economics, business law, marketing, and management. These subjects form the foundation, equipping students with essential knowledge about financial principles, market dynamics, legal frameworks, and organizational management strategies (Baker, 2019).

Business education graduates encounter various challenges as they transition into the workforce. These challenges include the need for practical, hands-on experience (Johnson, 2017), adapting to rapidly changing technologies and business landscapes (Parker, 2018), and developing effective communication and interpersonal skills (Garcia, 2019). Moreover, the

gap between theoretical knowledge acquired in classrooms and its real-world application poses a significant challenge for graduates (Robinson, 2021). In response to these challenges, innovative approaches have been introduced to business education. For example, experiential learning approaches, such as internships and collaborative projects with industry scheme thereby bridging the gap between theory and practice (Wang & Lee, 2020). Integrating simulation software and virtual reality into the curriculum allows students to engage in realistic business scenarios, enhancing their decision-making skills (Smith & Johnson, 2022). Additionally, mentorship programs and soft skills training workshops contribute to the holistic development of business education graduates, preparing them for successful careers (Clark & Martinez, 2023).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The role of business education in preparing graduates for the workforce cannot be overemphasized. Business education programs offered by federal universities in Northeast Nigeria aim to equip students with the necessary knowledge, skills, attitude and aptitude to thrive in various business sectors. However, the effectiveness of business education largely depends on its alignment with the industrial requirements prevalent in the region (Juliana & Robinson 2021). But unfortunately, the problem of unemployment among Business Education graduates is multi-faceted. One contributing factor is the perception among employers that these graduates often lack the practical skills knowledge attitude and aptitude required to excel in the workplace. This mismatch between the knowledge and skills attitude and aptitude imparted by the Business Education curriculum and the demands of the job market has left many graduates either unemployed or engaged in jobs that do not fully utilize their qualifications. This problem is not only a personal challenge for these graduates but also a significant concern for the broader society. A high rate of unemployment among educated youth can lead to social unrest, increased crime rates, and overall economic instability (Olabisi & Adebayo, 2017). Therefore, addressing the issue of unemployment among Business Education graduates is not only a matter of individual well-being but also crucial for the overall socioeconomic stability of Nigeria.

Deficit skills, knowledge, attitude and aptitude hinder employment opportunities to many graduates of business education programme. The central problem that will be addressed in this study will be the assessment of curriculum offered in Business Education programs within federal universities in North East Nigeria and the expected skills, knowledge, attitude and aptitude requirements for gainful employment of graduates by the industries. This misalignment will have profound implications for both individual graduates and the broader Nigerian economy. Individual graduates will likely encounter challenges in securing job opportunities that correspond to their educational qualifications, potentially leading to underemployment and dissatisfaction. From a macroeconomic perspective, this incongruence will result in a suboptimal utilization of human capital, potentially undermining the nation's capacity for innovation, entrepreneurship, and economic growth. Furthermore, this misalignment will likely contribute to elevated levels of graduate unemployment, which, in turn, will carry social and political repercussions, potentially jeopardizing individual well-being and the overall stability and progress of Nigeria as a nation.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The following objectives were raised to guide the study

- i. To determine the influence of skills acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria

- ii. To evaluate the influence of knowledge acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria.
- iii. To examine the influence of attitude acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- i. What is the influence of skills acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria.
- ii. What is the influence of knowledge acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria.
- iii. What is the influence of attitude acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria.

HYPOTHESES

Based on the research questions, the following hypothesis will be tested:

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of skills acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant knowledge acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria

H₀₃: There is no significant influence of attitude acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The research design that was adopted for this study was a descriptive survey. The population of the study consists of 276 respondents out of which 60 were business education lecturers and 216 were postgraduate students from the three Federal institutions located in the north-east zone where business education is taught. These institutions were: Modibbo Adama University, Yola, University of Maiduguri and Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University respectively. The entire population was used as sample for the study. This is because of the relatively small number of the respondents involved in the study. Structured questionnaire was used as an instrument for data collection. The instrument was divided into two sections. Section A were used to illicit information on the bio data of the respondent while section B were used to illicit information on the questionnaire items designed for the study. The instruments were validated by two experts from the Department of Vocational Education, who were not below the rank of a senior lecturer, from Modibbo Adama University, Yola. The reliability of the instrument was established through a pilot testing of the instrument at Taraba State, University, Jalingo using 30 respondents comprises both business education lecturers and their postgraduate students respectively. The results obtained were analyzed using split-half method. And the result from the two groups were tested using PPMC, which gave a reliability coefficient of 0.73 and was adjudged reliable for data collection.

The collected data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions at the benchmark of 2.50. All the mean responses of the respondents that were equal to or above 2.50 were considered agreed to the research questions. While, those mean responses of the respondents below 2.50 were considered disagreed to the research

questions. A linear regression analysis was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. All those hypotheses with a p-value of less than the Alpha value at 0.05 level of significance, were rejected. While those hypotheses with p-value above 0.05 level of significance were retained.

RESULTS

Research Question One: What is the influence of skills acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education student in north east Nigeria?

Table 1: Analysis of Mean Responses on the Influence of Skills Acquired on Industrial Requirement for Employment of Business Education Students in North -east Nigeria.

S/n	Questionnaire Items	Mean of Student	Std. Div	Mean of Teacher	Std. Div	Mean Average	Rmk
1	Curriculum of business education program is adequate to prepares me for the industrial Job.	2.99	.767	2.90	.911	2.95	Agree
2	Practical skills I have acquired during my studies align with the demands of the industries.	3.04	.733	2.97	.763	3.01	Agree
3	I have confident that the skills I have acquired through business education program prepare me well for employment opportunities in industries.	3.17	.688	2.96	.746	3.07	Agree
4	Employers in North East Nigeria value skills imparted by business education graduates.	2.94	.763	2.94	.752	2.94	Agree
5	There are challenges in applying the skills learned during my business education program to meet up with the industrial need.	2.85	.752	2.73	.869	2.79	Agree
6	My institution provided me with opportunity of practicing the knowledge learned through industrial training.	2.77	.669	2.83	.696	2.80	Agree
7	My program adequately emphasizes the development of soft skills (communication, teamwork, leadership, etc.) necessary for employment opportunities.	3.03	.741	2.92	.693	2.98	Agree
8	I feel confident that the skills acquired from business education program make me competitive in the job market.	3.26	2.56	2.90	.728	3.08	Agree
9	My acquired skill offers me networking opportunities with industry professionals, which enhances my chances of employment.	2.96	.712	3.01	.732	2.99	Agree
10	Industrial visits, or practical training programs plays a significant role in bridging the gap between the skills I have acquired and the requirements of industries.	2.87	.682	2.75	.681	2.81	Agree
Total		2.99		2.89		2.94	Agree

N= 276

From Table1 above, presents mean analysis on the influence of skill acquired on industrial requirement for employment opportunities of business education students in North east, Nigeria. The result revealed that items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10. This comprises of the two means from both students and their teachers. The two mean were further added and divided by 2 to find their average. The corresponding average mean were as follows:2.95, 3.01, 3.07, 2.94, 2.79, 2.80, 2.98, 3.08, 2.99 and 2.81 have all agreed with the research question one, that the skills acquired influence employment opportunities

of business education students in North east, Nigeria. In addition, the grand average mean of 2.94 which was above the benchmark of 2.50. This also suggested that the skills acquired influence industrial employment opportunities of business education students in North east, Nigeria.

Research Question Two: What is the influence of knowledge acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education student in north east Nigeria?

Table 2: Analysis of Mean Responses on the Influence of Knowledge Acquired on Industrial Requirement for Employment of Business Education Students in North -east Nigeria.

S/n	Questionnaire Items	Student Mean	Student Std. Div	Teacher Mean	Teacher Std. Div	Mean Average	Rmk
11	I have acquired knowledge adequately to align me with the industrial requirements for employment opportunities	2.96	.733	3.10	.727	3.03	Agree
12	Academic knowledge gained through business education program is relevant to the industrial requirements.	3.00	.714	3.08	.705	3.04	Agree
13	Theoretical knowledge I have acquired is effectively applicable to real-world industrial scenarios.	3.14	1.919	2.64	.846	2.89	Agree
14	My business education program enhances my ability to solve complex problems commonly encountered in industries.	2.96	.689	2.81	.837	2.89	Agree
15	I have acquired knowledge and skills adequately for modern industries.	2.97	.755	2.94	.761	2.96	Agree
16	My program equips me with industry-specific knowledge necessary for employment opportunities.	2.88	.701	2.90	.614	2.89	Agree
17	My program fosters critical thinking skills necessary for adapting a to dynamic industrial environments.	3.14	.668	2.92	.623	3.03	Agree
18	My education program keeps me informed about the current trends and developments in the industrial world	3.21	.664	3.03	.573	3.12	Agree
19	I have acquired research skills through my program that are valuable for addressing industry challenges and demands.	3.04	.681	2.81	.757	2.93	Agree
20	Knowledge acquired from my program seamlessly integrates with practical requirements of the industries in this region.	2.81	.739	2.93	.693	2.87	Agree
Total		3.01		2.92		2.96	Agree

N= 276

From Table 2 above, presents mean analysis on the influence of knowledge acquired on industrial requirement for employment opportunities of business education students in North east, Nigeria. The result revealed that items 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19 and 20. This comprises of the two means from both students and their teachers. The two mean were further added and divided to find their average. The corresponding average mean were as follows:3.03, 3.04, 2.89, 2.89, 2.96, 2.89, 3.03, 3.12, 2.93 and 2.87 have all again agreed with the research question two, that the knowledge acquired influence industrial employment opportunities of business education students in North east, Nigeria. In addition, the grand average mean is 2.96 which is above the benchmark of 2.50. This also suggested that the knowledge acquired influence industrial employment opportunities of business education students in North east, Nigeria.

Research Question Three: What is the influence of attitude acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education student in north east Nigeria?

Table 3: Analysis of Mean Responses on the Influence of Attitude Acquired on Industrial Requirement for Employment of Business Education Students in North -east Nigeria.

S/n	Questionnaire Items	Student Mean	Student Std. Div	Teacher Mean	Teacher Std. Div	Mean Average	Rmk
21	My business education program fosters the development of a strong work ethic necessary for employment in the industries.	2.90	.713	3.00	.819	2.95	Agree
22	The attitude acquired during your business education program influences your suitability for the employment in industries	2.80	.827	2.79	.819	2.80	Agree
23	Program enhances my professionalism, including punctuality, communication skills, and workplace etiquette.	2.77	.772	2.92	.718	2.85	Agree
24	I feel equipped with the attitude and mindset to adapt to various challenges and changes within industrial settings.	2.90	.672	2.91	.717	2.91	Agree
25	Program in stills in me a problem-solving attitude, enabling me to tackle challenges effectively in industrial settings.	2.99	.677	2.61	.880	2.80	Agree
26	I feel that my education program helps in building resilience, allowing me to bounce back from setbacks in the workplace.	2.91	.723	2.73	.697	2.82	Agree
27	I believe there is a correlation between the attitude cultivated through my business education program and meeting the requirements of industries in North East Nigeria?	2.98	.695	2.77	.645	2.88	Agree
28	Have encountered situations where a positive attitude has helped me overcome challenges to my pursuit of employment opportunities.	2.96	.651	2.81	.823	2.89	Agree
29	Business education Program provided me with skills necessary for career advancement in industries.	2.98	.741	2.96	.726	2.79	Agree
30	I am encouraged to demonstrate proactive behavior in discharging my industrial duties.	3.03	.779	3.23	.783	3.13	Agree
Total		2.92		2.87		2.90	Agree

N=276

From Table 3 above, presents mean analysis on the influence of attitude acquired on industrial requirement for employment opportunities of business education students in North east, Nigeria. The result revealed that items 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29 and 30. This comprises of the two means from both students and their teachers. The two mean were further added and divided to find their average. The corresponding average mean were as follows:2.95, 2.80, 2.85, 2.91, 2.80, 2.82, 2.88, 2.89, 2.79 and 3.13 have all again agreed with the research question three, that the attitude acquired influence industrial employment opportunities of business education students in North east, Nigeria. In addition, the grand average mean is 2.90 which is above the benchmark of 2.50. This also suggested that the knowledge acquired influence industrial employment opportunities of business education students in North east, Nigeria.

Test of Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of skills acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria.

Table 5a: Test of Linear Regression Analysis on the Influence of skills Acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1439.003	1	1439.003	88.802	.000 ^b
	Residual	4440.069	274	16.205		
	Total	5879.072	275			

a. Dependent Variable: INDUSTRIAL REQUIREMENT

b. Predictors: (Constant), SKILLS ACQUIRED

Table 5b. Model Summary on the Influence of skills Acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.495 ^a	.245	.242	4.02550

a. Predictors: (Constant), SKILLS ACQUIRED

From Tables 5 above, the linear regression analysis shows that there is a significant influence of skills acquired from business education curriculum for employment opportunities on industrial requirement by business education students. This is because the $F = 88.802$, ($df\ 275, 274$), $P < 0.05$ level of significance. Also, the computed p-value (0.000) which is less than the alpha value of 0.05 level of significant, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This means that the skills acquired from business education curriculum has a positive relationship with industrial requirement for employment opportunities of business education students in North east, Nigeria with R-square value of (0.495), which indicates that, more than 49 % of the industrial requirement for employment opportunities was attributed to the skills acquired by business education students.

H₀₂: There is no significant knowledge acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria.

Table 6a: Test of Linear Regression Analysis on the Influence of Knowledge Acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1466.654	1	1466.654	91.076	.000 ^b
	Residual	4412.418	274	16.104		
	Total	5879.072	275			

a. Dependent Variable: INDUSTRIAL REQUIREMENT

b. Predictors: (Constant), KNOWLEDGE ACQUIRED

Table 6b. Model Summary on the Influence of Knowledge Acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.499 ^a	.249	.247	4.01294

a. Predictors: (Constant), KNOWLEDGE ACQUIRED

From Tables 6 above, the linear regression analysis shows that there is a significant influence of knowledge acquired from business education curriculum for employment opportunities on industrial requirement by business education students. This is because the $F = 91.076$, (df 275, 274), $P < 0.05$ level of significance. Also, the computed p-value (0.000) which is less than the alpha value of 0.05 level of significant, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This means that the knowledge acquired from business education curriculum has a positive relationship with industrial requirement for employment opportunities of business education students in North east, Nigeria with R-square value of (0.499), which indicates that, more than 50 % of the industrial requirement for employment opportunities was attributed to the knowledge acquired by business education students.

H₀₃: There is no significant influence of attitude acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria.

Table 7a: Test of Linear Regression Analysis on the Influence of Attitude Acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria.

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1511.924	1	1511.924	94.860	.000 ^b
	Residual	4367.149	274	15.938		
	Total	5879.072	275			

a. Dependent Variable: INDUSTRIAL REQUIREMENT

b. Predictors: (Constant), ATTITUDE ACQUIRED

Table 7b. Model Summary on the Influence of Attitude Acquired on industrial requirement for employment of business education graduates in north east Nigeria.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.507 ^a	.257	.254	3.99230

a. Predictors: (Constant), ATTITUDE ACQUIRED

From Tables 7 above, the linear regression analysis shows that there is a significant influence of attitude acquired from business education curriculum for employment opportunities on industrial requirement by business education students. This is because the $F = 94.860$, (df 275, 274), $P < 0.05$ level of significance. Also, the computed p-value (0.000) which is less than the alpha value of 0.05 level of significant, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This means that the attitude acquired from business education curriculum has a positive relationship with industrial requirement for employment opportunities of business education students in North east, Nigeria with R-square value of (0.507), which indicates that, more than 51% of the industrial requirement for employment opportunities was attributed to the attitude acquired by business education students.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The findings of study revealed that the skills acquired influence industrial employment opportunities of business education students in North east, Nigeria. This is also in agreement with the result from the test of null hypotheses one. the linear regression analysis also shows that there is a significant influence between skills acquired from business education curriculum for employment opportunities and industrial requirement by business education students. This finding corroborated with the findings of Elizabeth and Abosede (2023) who asserted that there is a significant influence between Business Education curriculum content and the entrepreneurial skills development of Business Education students in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. In a similar study conducted by Okon and Edet (2023) also found that a strong relationship exists between Business Education curriculum components and the development of entrepreneurial skills among undergraduates in Cross River State. Business education curriculum equips students with the acquisition of planning skills that would be needed for their entrepreneurial venture in order to succeed and also develop their entrepreneurial venture in order to succeed and also develop their communication skills which is very essential in the world of work (Iweyah, 2023).

The findings of study revealed that the Knowledge acquired influence industrial employment opportunities of business education students in North east, Nigeria. This is also in agreement with the result from the test of null hypotheses two. the linear regression analysis also shows that there is a significant influence between Knowledge acquired from business education curriculum for employment opportunities and industrial requirement by business education students. This finding corroborated with the findings of Agwu (2018) averred that business education curriculum enables students to acquire the skills necessary for entrepreneurship and also equip them with the right skills that would enable them to engage in a life of work in offices as well as for self-employment upon graduation. The author opined that business education curriculum is a curriculum that endows its learner with appropriate knowledge, skills and attitudes which enables them to harness the natural and human potentials in order to improve the quality of life environment they find themselves. Amadike and Obara (2020) observed that some skills and knowledge of these teachers are likely to become obsolete because of lack of updating them, hence they need to update themselves through attending seminars, workshops, conferences and so on, which enables students acquire adequate knowledge, skills and competencies that are appropriate for their areas of responsibility that would enable them meet the needs of labour workforce. Amadike and Obara (2020) also observed that poor teachers of business education programme hinders the students from developing intellectual skills and knowledge that would equip them to contribute significantly to the society and also denies them the ability to satisfy the requirements of the labour market which causes unemployment and poverty upon graduation.

The findings of study also revealed that the Attitude acquired influence industrial employment opportunities of business education students in North east, Nigeria. This is also in agreement with the result from the test of null hypotheses two. the linear regression analysis also shows that there is a significant influence between Attitude acquired from business education curriculum for employment opportunities and industrial requirement by business education students. This finding corroborated with the findings of Petty and Briñol (2018) who asserted that attitude as "a mental and neural state of readiness, organized through experience, exerting a directive or dynamic influence upon the individual's response to all objects and situations with which it is related. According to the recent studies, showing that the attitude is related with a category of problems concerning "how individuals perceived the world" and how they "behave", the definition of the attitude should refer to "people, groups, ideas, and objects", which mainly express whether individuals "like or dislike them", and the main meaning of this concept is articulated on cognitive, affective and behavioral aspects (Florin, 2020).

CONCLUSION

Based on the above findings, the study concluded that industrial requirement and business education curriculum had a positive relationship with an employment opportunity of business education graduates in north-east, Nigeria. If skills acquisition, knowledge, attitude and aptitude are given required support, the students will graduate with ready-made skills that will guarantee their employment opportunity anywhere they found themselves. Because the study showed that the students were actually equipped with requisite fundamentals that they need for their growth and development as business educators. And anything short of this rudiment may be detrimental.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study, the study recommends that:

1. The University administration should emphasize more on students' skills acquisition as this was found to be a requirement for the industrial employment opportunities for business education graduates. Equipping the students with skills is tantamount to given them an industrial job.
2. The University administration should also emphasize on knowledge acquisition as this was found to be fundamental requirement for employment opportunity by business education graduate in the industrial workforce.
3. The University administration should emphasize more on students Attitude and aptitude which are two psychological thread that are fundamental to employment opportunities in the industrial workforce.

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